

ROSIE

D8.2: ROSiE branding: logo, website and social media

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1 ROSiE logo

The ROSiE logo (main idea, color scheme and aesthetics) was presented at D8.1, since it stands as a substantive part of the dissemination of the project. It reflects the main concept that is “**Connecting stakeholders and lay people through dialogue**” (Figure 1). This overlapping speech bubbles logo represents the importance ROSiE gives to all types of foreseen engagement processes. Other variations of the logo have also been presented at D8.1.

Figure 1: The ROSiE logo – the two basic variations.

2 ROSiE website

This deliverable contains information on ROSiE’s website (<https://rosie-project.eu/>) and its social media sites (Twitter and LinkedIn pages). ROSiE’s website acts as a hub, where all online dissemination channels converge. Twitter and LinkedIn pages of the project can be easily reached through the front page of the website. Additionally, the Twitter account has an active window at the bottom of the front page, where the activity of ROSiE and other projects is visible.

NTUA started designing the website and created the Social Media sites even before the official start of the project, in close collaboration with the project’s coordinators. The non-public version of the website was presented at the coordinating entity, where there was the chance to comment on the different elements of the website (i.e. content, design, and aesthetics). NTUA implemented all needed amendments. The design and aesthetics of the Social Media sites are for branding purposes adjusted to and in line with the website.

ROSiE’s website was launched on the 24th of June 2021, for the necessary final finishing touches to be applied in the real environment (i.e. not in a mock-up form) and will be widely disseminated through the existing social media channels on the 31st of June – on time for the MS2 to be successfully reached.

Technical specifications

ROSiE’s website has been launched through the official server of NTUA. The current version of the website is based on the popular content management system WordPress. Relevant technologies: PHP, MySQL database, WordPress. Future updated versions of the website will

extend the existing infrastructure and use more flexible web development frameworks like Laravel PHP to better support advanced usage scenarios.

3 ROSiE website: brief description

The 1st version of ROSiE’s website was launched on the 24th of June 2021 and most of its content can be reached by scrolling down. This option was chosen, since at this early point of the project’s timeline, there is not a large volume of information to be communicated. NTUA, in cooperation with UiO, decided to refrain from adding pop-up menus and keep the website as simple as possible, in order to spread the word of the project’s basic objectives, key concepts, vision, challenges and mission as efficient as possible. Below there is a series of screen captures of the project's website.

Figure 2: The upper part of the ROSiE website front page; it acts as the welcome or the “reception” area for the visitor. The background figure represents the collective effort from ROSiE consortium, Advisory Board members and involved stakeholders.

Figure 3: The basic information about ROSIE is visibly presented right below the introductory part of the front page (Figure 2).

Figure 4: The challenges of the ROSIE project. The background figure represents the collective effort from ROSIE consortium, Advisory Board members and involved stakeholders. It is the background figure also at the LinkedIn account.

Figure 5: The ROSIE key concepts that guide the visitor who is not familiar with the terminology. Each point expands when clicked to provide relevant information (here we see the Responsible research and innovation points expanded).

Figure 6: The ROSIE basic objectives and target groups. The objectives expand when clicked, as the list of key concepts (the figure here is shown in a smaller magnification with respect to the previous figures).

Figure 7: The ROSIE timeline that has the aim to present the work programme to the visitor with just a glance. At the future each square presenting a specific activity will be clickable.

Figure 8: The end of ROSIE's front page with information of our funders.

4 ROSiE social media presence (update from D8.1)

As it has been described at D8.1, dissemination through social media networks (LinkedIn and Twitter) will focus on providing pointed, succinct and highly accessible findings. The dissemination will link to the background material provided on the web page whenever this is appropriate, to allow interested audiences to access additional information.

In 31 June, the time of the milestone for the website launch, the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of the project will disseminate this important event and from then on the dissemination/communication strategy will start to be in full fledge. Approximately three months after the launch of the project's twitter account @rosie_open has 142 followers. This is a satisfactory number, taking into account that ROSiE has not yet been launched, while no findings have yet been available for dissemination and communication.

5 Deviations from DoA

No deviations from DoA.

